

Gas chromatography analysis of fatty acid esters and free fatty acids for the evaluation of lipase performance in textile treatment and washing

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ABSTRACT

Fatty acid esters (FAE) can be found in textiles in many forms, both in manufacturing and as components of consumer products. Removal of FAEs and the resulting free fatty acids (FFA) poses a problem which can partially be solved by using enzymes. Lipases can potentially aid the removal of FAE-based spin-finishes and fatty stains from textile fibres. However, monitoring substrates and/or products of enzyme reactions is difficult, mainly because FAE and the resulting FFA are not sufficiently volatile for conventional analysis by gas chromatography (GC). Therefore, derivatisation is usually performed before analysis. Here, two methodologies for the analysis of FAE and FFA in textiles by GC (with mass spectrometer or flame ionisation detectors) were developed using methylation and silylation. While methylation allows for the analysis of total fatty acids (FAE + FFA), silylation allows the analysis of FFA/diacylglycerols/monoacylglycerols. Derivatisation of the sample by acid-catalysed methylation without prior extraction was found effective for total fatty acids analysis in both fat/oil soiled textiles and raw textiles containing spin-finishes. Silylation with *N,O*-bis(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide: trimethylchlorosilane allowed for the quantification of FFA in raw textiles, with a marked increase in concentration of FFA being observed after treatment with lipases. These derivatisation strategies allowed the evaluation of the performance of lipase-facilitated washing of textiles, by both (i) assessment of the efficiency of the overall washing process by the quantification of the FAE/FFA remaining on the textile, and (ii) determination of the activity of used lipases by quantification of the enzymatic hydrolysis products.

1. Introduction

Lipases (EC 3.1.1.3) can generically be defined as enzymes that catalyse the hydrolysis of water-insoluble triacylglycerols (TAG) into diacylglycerols (DAG), monoacylglycerols (MAG), free fatty acids (FFA), and glycerol (Verger, 1997). This is not a comprehensive classification since some lipases, for example the pancreatic lipase, lack activity towards specific positions of the acylglycerol (2-position in this case) (Mattson and Volpenhein, 1968), leading to an incomplete hydrolysis of

the TAG. On the other hand, lipases often possess substrate promiscuity, showing activity towards other soluble and insoluble esters (Nini et al., 2001), although they may also show substrate specificity depending on the FA present in the acylglycerol (Berger and Schneider, 1991; Park and Park, 2022). Currently, lipases are applied in multiple industrial processes and consumer products (Bornscheuer, 2018; Houde et al., 2004; Jaeger and Eggert, 2002; Welsh et al., 1989). However, the analysis of the real substrates and/or products in industrial reaction media and matrices, such as textiles, is more complex than when lipases are studied

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using standard laboratory substrates.

The products of the hydrolysis of TAG are generally less hydrophobic than the original molecule, and are therefore easier to remove from matrixes like textiles during washing (Aaslyng et al., 1991). Lipases are thus frequently applied in laundry detergents (Houde et al., 2004). Other processes involving textile matrixes containing fatty acid esters (FAE) can also benefit from the application of lipases. Cotton sizes – mostly composed of starch and other polymers – are added to cotton fibres prior to weaving to prevent fibre breakage (Roth et al., 2023). They must be removed afterwards, before dyeing, to allow the adhesion of the dyes to the fibres. In addition to the commonly used amylases (Regan, 1962), lipases may also be used in the desizing process if FAE were included as lubricants during sizing of the fibres (Rowe, 1999). Spin-finishes, mixtures of lubricants, anti-static agents, emulsifiers, and other components, must be added to synthetic fibres during their production, prior to the manufacturing of the textile (Bajaj, 1997; Roth et al., 2023). Like cotton sizes, spin-finishes must be removed from the textile before the dyeing process, as their hydrophobicity prevents an homogeneous distribution of the dye through the fibres (Roth et al., 2023). This is usually performed by surfactant or solvent-base washes. FAE and acylglycerols are often used as lubricants in spin-finishes (Bajaj, 1997). The potential use of lipases to aid their removal is now being explored, as they can reduce rinsing steps, improve dyeing efficiency, and facilitate discolouration and water neutralisation. Life cycle assessments indicate that enzymatic treatments can markedly lower the carbon footprint of fibre processing, with 1 g of enzyme saving 0.42 kg – 1.0 kg CO₂ per kilogram of dry yarn, particularly relevant given that up to 10% of fabric is currently wasted due to residual impurities remaining on the fibres (Molina-Espeja et al., 2023). The exact composition of the spin-finishes present in a synthetic fibre is often unknown to a textile manufacturer. Testing a lipase against multiple FAE potentially present in spin-finishes is thus not a viable option for the determination of its usefulness. The specific conditions of the textile treatment, such as the low water activity imposed by the application of the enzyme through a padding process, or interactions between the substrates and fibres, further limit such evaluations. Methods for the direct analysis of the FAE, FFA, and acylglycerols contained in textiles are thus paramount to make such assessments.

Multiple methods have been applied in the past for the analysis of the removed fatty stains with washing. Lipid stains prepared with pigments such as Sudan red can be determined by measurement of the surface reflectance (Gotoh, 2010), or qualitatively assessed by observation of the colour change (Grbavčić et al., 2011). For such assays to be valid, a preferably quantitative relation between amount of pigment and stain removal must be established. However, this strategy cannot be applied to samples such as those of raw textiles containing spin-finishes, as they already contain the FAE that are intended to be removed, whose composition is not known a priori. Several studies also analysed lipid removal by a simple measurement of the mass of both stained and washed textiles (García-Silvera et al., 2018; Li et al., 2014), or of the lipids extracted from the textile after washing (Grbavčić et al., 2011; Kamini et al., 1998). These analyses require the treatment and washing of substantial amounts of textile, especially if the initial concentration of FAE in the textile is low. Other more complex strategies have also been proposed. Obendorf et al. analysed the washing of stains, with and without the addition of lipases, by scanning electron microscopy after staining with osmium tetroxide, allowing for the observation of the different stages of removal of lard from cotton fibres (Obendorf et al., 2001). FAE/acylglycerols with radio-labelled FA have also been used in evaluations of the washing of lipid-stained textiles, with lipid removal being evaluated by the measurement of the radioactivity of the sample with scintillation counters (Flipsen et al., 1998; Obendorf et al., 2001; Scott, 1963). However, this technique is limited to the evaluation of the removal of stains produced by the experimentalist, thus precluding its application in the testing of spin-finish/cotton size removal. Furthermore, these substrates usually are significantly more expensive than

their non-labelled forms. Distinct methodologies, allowing for the evaluation of the removal of lipids/FAE from textiles, especially from samples natively containing these contaminants, are therefore required. Different chromatographic techniques may be of use in this regard. Chromatographic analyses would be of particular interest in the study of the application of lipases in washing processes, as they may allow for the quantification of the distinct products/substrates of lipases, unlike the unspecific methodologies mentioned previously. Chromatography may thus allow the assessment of not only the removal of lipids/FAE, but also the quantification of the activity of the lipase towards the target contaminants.

Chromatographic techniques are routinely applied to the analysis of fats and oils, in particular, gas chromatography (GC) and high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) (Buchgraber et al., 2004). GC analysis was used in this work. Lipid samples are usually, but not exclusively, subjected to derivatisation procedures before GC analysis to increase the volatility and thermal stability of the analytes (Ahuja, 1976; Řezanka et al., 2016). Analysis of underivatized TAG is possible in high-temperature GC protocols (Ruiz-Samblás et al., 2015). However, analysis at such high temperatures can lead to thermal degradation of polyunsaturated FA (Buchgraber et al., 2004). It also requires the use of columns that are stable at the temperatures required for such analysis, potentially above 350 °C (Ruiz-Samblás et al., 2015).

Among the various derivatisation strategies used to enhance the volatility and thermal stability of lipids for GC analysis, methylation and silylation are the two most widely applied. Methylation converts FFA and FA-containing lipids into fatty acid methyl esters (FAME), whereas silylation produces volatile silyl derivatives by substituting active hydrogens in hydroxyl- and carboxyl-containing molecules. Other derivatisation approaches exist, but these two remain the most broadly used in routine lipid analysis.

Methylation can be applied to FAE, including acylglycerols, and FFA. For FAE, the alcohol moiety is replaced by methanol (Cruz-Hernandez and Destailats, 2016), which may be performed in a single step by a transesterification reaction, or preceded by a saponification step (Christie, 1989; Eder, 1995). Several types of methylation reactions, derivatising FFA and/or FAE, have been described in the literature (Christie, 1989; Li and Watkins, 2001). In general, these reactions are performed in methanol and are catalysed by an acid or base. Different catalysts possess advantages and disadvantages. For instance, sulfuric acid-catalysed reactions simultaneously methylate FAE and FFA, but require heating. Alternatively, a sodium methoxide-catalysed reaction can be performed at room temperature, but only leads to the derivatisation of FAE (Eder, 1995), as occurs with most base-catalysed methylations (Christie, 1989; Kramer et al., 1997; Schuchardt and Lopes, 1988). Methylation is frequently applied to fats and oils for the determination of their FA profile (Gutnikov, 1995), as it can provide information, e.g., about the nutritional characteristics of a fat or oil (Seppänen-Laakso et al., 2002), or about the adulteration of oils (Lim et al., 2020). GC analysis following methylation has also been applied previously to the evaluation of lipase treatment in textile washing. Fujii et al. evaluated the effect of a lipase in the removal of olive oil from fabrics by GC analysis, after extraction of the oil from the textile, methylation of acylglycerols with a sodium hydroxide-methanol solution, and methylation of FFA with a boron trifluoride-methanol solution (Fujii et al., 1986). Oil removal was calculated as the ratio between the total weight of fatty acids present before and after the wash, as determined by the GC analysis.

Silylation encompasses different reactions leading to the replacement of active hydrogen atoms in OH, NH, and SH groups with silyl groups, most commonly trimethylsilyl (TMS) groups (Halket and Zaikin, 2003). For the purpose of lipid analysis, the reaction with hydroxyl and carboxyl groups are particularly important, as it allows for the derivatisation of FFA and MAG/DAG into silyl esters and ethers, respectively. TMS derivatives of FFA, MAG, and DAG, can be analysed simultaneously by GC, avoiding prior chromatographic separation (Bruschweiler and

Dieffenbacher, 1991; Firestone, 1994; Lau et al., 2005; Plank and Lorbeer, 1995), for example by solid phase extraction (Ruiz-Gutiérrez and Pérez-Camino, 2000) followed by derivatisation of separate lipid fractions. However, some authors still suggest a prior extraction step to selectively remove TAG (Fagan et al., 2004; Pérez-Camino et al., 1996). Simultaneous analysis of TAG has also been described, although this requires high oven temperatures due to their low volatility (Lau et al., 2005; Michael-Jubeli et al., 2011; Plank and Lorbeer, 1995), as mentioned previously. To the best of our knowledge, silylation has not previously been applied to evaluate lipase-assisted removal of acylglycerols/FAE from textiles, as previous studies have relied mainly on GC analysis after methylation of fatty acids.

Most published studies are carried out with substrates suitable for laboratory use, such as those that change colour after molecular alteration, but real substrates are much more valuable to assess enzyme performance for industrial applications. In the present study, different methods of methylation and silylation were tested with the aim of establishing protocols for the analysis of the performance of lipases in the treatment of textiles containing FAE. Target analytes include TAG or other lipids present in standard stains used in laundry detergent testing, and other FAE present in spin-finishes and sizing mixtures used in the textile industry. Methylation of the lipids was used to evaluate total concentration of FAE and FFA, by means of the quantification of the corresponding FAME, subsequently referred as total FA. Silylation was used to analyse the products of the lipase reactions (FFA + DAG + MAG). Finally, two sets of assays were performed to validate the application of the method proposed, where stained and raw textiles (that is, industrial textiles that have not been treated and dyed) were treated with lipases with the aim of improving the removal of FAE.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Textile samples

Standard stained textiles (Table 1) were obtained from the Center for Testmaterials (The Netherlands). Raw textiles containing spin-finishes, as well as the corresponding desized and scoured textiles produced using current industrial processes (Table 2), were manufactured and provided by Schoeller Textiles AG (Switzerland).

2.2. Reagents

Palmitic acid, monopalmitin, *N,O*-bis(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide (BSTFA), and BSTFA: trimethylchlorosilane 99:1 (BSTFA+TMCS (99:1)) were purchased from TCI Chemicals. *N*-Methyl-*N*-(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide (MSTFA) was purchased from Thermo Scientific. HPLC grade chloroform, methanol, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and *n*-hexane were obtained from Fischer Scientific. 95–97% Sulfuric acid and CaCl₂·2H₂O were purchased from Merck. 4-(2-Hydroxyethyl)piperazine-1-propanesulfonic acid (EPPS) buffer was purchased from Acros Organics. NaCl, 4-(2-hydroxyethyl)piperazine-1-ethanesulfonic acid (HEPES), and dipalmitin were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich.

Lipases PEH_Paes PE-H_Y250S (subsequently referred to as Y250S) (Bollinger et al., 2020b), EstLip_Dim_#008 (subsequently referred to as

Table 1
Standard stained textiles obtained from Center for Testmaterials.

Code	Stain	Textile substrate
C-S-61	Beef-fat	Woven Cotton
PC-09	Oil	Polyester/Cotton
C-S-05 s	Mayonnaise	Woven Cotton
C-S-10	Butterfat	Woven Cotton
P-S-16	Lipstick	Polyester
C-S-17	Fluid make-up	Woven Cotton
PC-S-132	Sebum	Polyester/Cotton

Table 2

Raw textiles, manufactured by Schoeller Textiles AG.

Textile	Fibre Composition				Type	Mass/area ratio (g m ⁻²)
	Cotton	Elastane	Polyamide	Polyester		
C1	92%	8%			Woven	240
PA1		8%	92%		Woven	180
PA2		8%	92%		Woven	280
PA3		12%	88%		Woven	135
PA4		20%	80%		Warp-Knitted	160
PE1				100%	Woven	100

Dim_#008) (Bollinger et al., 2020a; Masomian et al., 2013), and Lip_{MRD9} bearing the Val161Ser substitution (subsequently referred to as Lip9) (Vidal et al., 2024) were produced with *Pichia pastoris* as the expression host by Biosynth GmbH (Austria) using their proprietary expression technology. Lyophilised enzyme preparations were used after dilution in an appropriate buffer.

2.3. Lipid extraction

FFA/FAE were extracted by adapting the Bligh & Dyer method (Bligh and Dyer, 1959) prior to derivatisation by silylation, and in some cases before methylation (see section 2.4). Lipid extraction was performed on circular cut samples with a diameter of 6 mm for standard stained textiles. For textiles containing spin finishes, square cut samples of 1 cm², or 2.25 cm² for PE1 (due to its smaller mass to area ratio) were used. The area of each sample was made taking into account the initial concentration of lipids. To each sample, 1.5 mL of methanol and 0.75 mL of chloroform were added. Samples were stirred for 2 h at 250 rpm in an orbital shaker, after which 0.75 mL of chloroform and 0.75 mL of ultrapure water were added. Samples were mixed on a vortex mixer until a uniform turbid mixture was achieved. Phase separation was achieved by a combination of cooling at −20 °C and gentle centrifugation. The lower chloroform phase was then retrieved and dried in a low pressure evaporator (RapidVap, Labconco) under a partial vacuum of 175 mbar to 80 mbar, at 40 °C. Dried extracts were stored at −20 °C until derivatisation. The recovery rates of the Bligh and Dyer extraction of palmitic acid, monopalmitin, and dipalmitin were determined for five concentrations of standards, ranging between a mixture of 375 μM of each of the three standards, and a mixture containing 15 μM of palmitic acid, 5.1 μM of monopalmitin, and 3.9 μM of dipalmitin. The recovery rate was defined as the ratio between the concentration determined after silylation (see section 2.5) of samples subjected to extraction, and the concentration determined for samples derivatised directly, without prior extraction. Reactions were performed at least in duplicate.

2.4. Methylation

Three different methylation strategies were tested on both sets of textiles: a base-catalysed methylation with the Instant-FAME™ protocol (from MIDI Inc.) (Kunitsky et al., 2006) applied directly to textile samples, and a sulfuric acid-catalysed methylation (de Carvalho et al., 2014), applied to extracts from textiles, or directly to textile samples. Sulfuric acid-catalysed methylation was chosen for its ability to simultaneously esterify FFA and transesterify FAE without the need for a previous hydrolysis step (Christie, 1989). The Instant-FAME™ protocol was evaluated as an alternative due to the short reaction time, and for not requiring heating. For direct application of derivatisation reactions, the analysed sample areas of each textile were similar to those described for the extraction procedure.

For the sulfuric acid-catalysed methylation, 0.75 mL of sulfuric acid at 2.5% (v/v) in methanol was added to each sample. Samples were incubated at 80 °C for 90 min. After cooling to room temperature, 0.35 mL of *n*-hexane and 0.35 mL of NaCl at 9.8 g L⁻¹ were added, and the

sample was vigorously shaken for 2 min on a vortex mixer and centrifuged for 1 min at 10,000 \times g. The top hexane layer was then recovered for analysis. The Instant-FAME™ protocol was applied according to the instructions of the manufacturer. All reactions were performed at least in duplicate.

2.5. Silylation

Three different silylation reagents, reacting to produce trimethylsilyl-esters/ethers were tested, namely: (i) MSTFA, (ii) BSTFA, and (iii) BSTFA+TMCS (99:1). The silylation reagents were first used to derivatise FFA in PA1 and C1 textiles, and also mixtures of palmitic acid, monopalmitin, and dipalmitin (each at a concentration of 0.375 mM). Firstly, the dried extracts were dissolved in 0.9 mL of *n*-hexane for the FFA/MAG/DAG mixture, or 0.86 mL of *n*-hexane and 0.04 mL of DMSO for raw textile extracts. To each sample, 0.1 mL of silylation reagent was then added, the sample was briefly mixed, and then incubated at 70 °C for 90 min. The samples were left to cool to room temperature and subsequently mixed before recovery for analysis. Relative concentrations of MSTFA ranging between 5% and 20% (v/v) were further tested in the silylation of the mixture of palmitic acid, monopalmitin and dipalmitin (each at a concentration of 0.375 mM). For BSTFA+TMCS (99:1), concentrations ranging between 5% and 20% (v/v) were also tested for the silylation of PA1 extracts under the same conditions. The volume of *n*-hexane was adjusted to keep a final reaction volume of 1 mL. At 20% BSTFA+TMCS (99:1), DMSO became miscible with the *n*-hexane phase. At lower concentrations, a distinct phase of this solvent was visible in the cooled samples. Therefore, for raw textile samples, only the top phase of the sample (mixture of *n*-hexane and silylation reagent) was recovered for analysis.

Extracts from raw and enzyme-treated textiles were derivatised with BSTFA+TMCS (99:1) at 10% (v/v), under the reaction conditions described previously. MSTFA at 10% (v/v) was used for the silylation of extracts from both lipase treated and untreated standard stained textiles, with DMSO being omitted for these samples. All reactions were performed in duplicate.

2.6. GC analysis

GC analysis was performed with an Agilent Technologies 7820A gas chromatograph equipped with an Agilent Technologies 5977E MSD mass spectrometer (GC–MS) and 7693 Autosampler, and with an Agilent Technologies 6890N GC equipped with a flame ionisation detector (GC–FID), and a 7683B Series autosampler. Data acquisition, quantification, and chromatogram analysis for the GC–MS system were made with the MassHunter Workstation Software suite from Agilent Technologies: GC/MS Acquisition version B.07.03.2129, Quantitative Analysis version B.07.01, and Qualitative Analysis B.07.00, respectively. Compound identification from mass spectra was performed by comparison with the NIST Mass Spectral Search Program for the NIST/EPA/NIH Mass Spectral Library, version 2.2, and by injection of lipid standards when available. For the GC–FID system, data acquisition and analysis were performed using the GC ChemStation revision B.02.01-SR1 from Agilent Technologies. Additionally, Sherlock software version 6.2 from MIDI Inc. was used for the identification of FAME. Both GC systems were equipped with an Agilent J&W Ultra 2, 5% phenyl methyl siloxane capillary column, with 25 m in length, 200 μ m of inner diameter, and a film thickness of 0.33 μ m.

Similar analyses protocols were used for silylated samples of raw textiles and methylated samples of both textile sets, in both GC systems. A volume of 2 μ L of sample was injected into the injector set at 250 °C, with a split ratio of 30:1 in the GC–FID system, and 20:1 in the GC–MS system. Initial oven temperature was set at 190 °C, with a temperature ramp of 10 °C min^{-1} until 285 °C was reached, followed by a 60 °C min^{-1} ramp up to 310 °C, with a hold time of 1 min, or 25 min for silylated samples of standard stains. Hydrogen was used as carrier gas in

the GC–FID system, and helium in the GC–MS system. The gas flow rate through the columns was set at 1.2 mL min^{-1} . For the GC–FID, the detector was set at 300 °C, or 310 °C for silylated samples of standard stains. GC–MS was operated in scan mode, with a range of 80 *m/z* to 400 *m/z* for methylated samples, 80 *m/z* to 550 *m/z* for silylated samples of raw textiles, and 80 *m/z* to 700 *m/z* for silylated samples of standard stains. MS ion source was set at 230 °C, and the quadrupole at 150 °C. Quantification of FA was made using external calibration curves obtained for: palmitic acid for FFA and total FA; monopalmitin for MAG; and, dipalmitin for DAG. Palmitic acid was derivatised by acid methylation or silylation with BSTFA+TMCS (99:1), as described previously. Monopalmitin and dipalmitin were derivatised with MSTFA.

2.7. Enzymatic treatment trials

The removal of spin-finishes from raw textiles was tested with the enzymes Y250S, Dim_#008 and Lip9, in small scale trials performed with a benchtop Foulard machine (two roller horizontal/vertical paddler, Type «HVF 500», from Mathis) on PA1, PE1 and C1 textiles. These textiles were selected as models of the three fibre combinations under study: PA1 as a model of a polyamide + elastane textile; PE1, a polyester textile; and C1, a cotton + elastane textile. Enzyme solutions were prepared at 16 g L^{-1} in HEPES buffer at 50 mM, pH 7, with 50 mM CaCl_2 . Textile samples, with approximately 300 cm^2 , were padded twice with this solution, at pick-ups (ratio of mass of retained solution to initial mass of the textile) of approximately 75% for PA1, 60% for PE1, and 47% for C1. Samples were incubated for 24 h at room temperature, in sealed bags. Following incubation, textiles were washed with water at 60 °C for 10 min under gentle stirring, padded (without solution) to remove excess liquid, and dried at 150 °C in an oven (LABDRYER Type «LTE», from Mathis). Textile samples were analysed after silylation and methylation, in duplicate. Textiles submitted to the industrial pretreatment (solvent or surfactant-based washes) were also analysed.

The ability of the enzyme Y250S to hydrolyse fatty stains was evaluated with Beef-fat-stained fabric (C-S-61) and Mayonnaise-stained fabric (C-S-05 s), selected as models of a fat soil, and of a soil composed by an oil/protein emulsion, respectively. In 1.5 mL centrifuge tubes, a volume of EPPS buffer at 100 mM, pH 8, with or without 75 mg L^{-1} of lyophilised enzyme preparation, was added to each sample of stained textile (approximately 6 mm in diameter) to achieve a ratio of 1 mL buffer per 10 mg of textile. Samples were incubated for 5 h at 40 °C under agitation at 500 rpm. Textile samples were then removed from the buffer and dried on an evaporator at 40 °C under a partial vacuum of 80 mbar. Samples were stored at –20 °C before derivatisation, if necessary. All assays were done at least in duplicate.

2.8. Error analysis

The average error associated with the GC quantification of each FAME was $\pm 2.27\%$, quoted for a confidence interval of 99.5%. Errors were calculated based on nine analysis of standard solutions.

3. Results and discussion

To assess the efficiency of lipases for the removal of FAE in textiles, analysis protocols were tested for the quantification of FFA, DAG, and MAG: while the total concentration of FAE and FFA was determined by analysis of the corresponding FAME obtained by methylation, silylation allowed the analysis of the FFA, DAG, and MAG. Both methods were initially validated as stated in the following section.

3.1. Methods validation

Two different GC systems were used in this work: a GC–FID and a GC–MS. Since both systems had similar columns and were run with the same temperature protocols, samples analysed in the two systems

resulted in similar chromatograms, with retention times (RT) presenting a linear correlation between the two. The differences in RT resulted mainly from the gases used as mobile phases: helium in the GC-MS and hydrogen in the GC-FID. Derivatised samples of stained and raw textiles, before and after enzyme treatment, were initially analysed in both systems, with GC-MS being used for compound identification, and GC-FID being simultaneously used for quantification of lipids on both untreated and enzyme treated samples. An exception was made for the comparison of the three methylation strategies, with quantification being performed solely in the GC-MS system. The GC-FID system was chosen for subsequent quantification analysis for its greater sensitivity, especially towards silylated FA, and improved reproducibility of the analysis. Additionally, peak separation between unsaturated FA isomers, with the same number of carbon atoms, was less accurate in the GC-MS analysis than in the GC-FID. The software Sherlock v. 6.2 was used to identify these FA in the GC-FID analysis, by comparison with the built-in database.

The analysis of total FA, corresponding to the sum of the concentration of all identified FA, was performed on standard stained textiles using both the Instant-FAME™ protocol and the acid-catalysed methylation. These methylation protocols were conducted with or without prior extraction of the lipids by the Bligh & Dyer method. The results showed that the Instant-FAME™ protocol resulted in similar, if not better, derivatisation of the FAE and acylglycerols present in the standard stained textiles than the acid-catalysed reactions (Fig. 1-A). The advantage of this protocol is that it is much faster than the others tested, requiring ca. 3 min for sample preparation (Alexander, 2012), versus the ca. 2 h required for the direct acid methylation protocol, with an additional 3 h if the Bligh & Dyer extraction is performed. However, the Instant-FAME™ protocol performed considerably worse with the compounds present in raw textiles (Fig. 1-B). This hints at the presence

Fig. 1. Total FA relative to the total FA obtained with acid methylation after Bligh & Dyer extraction, for the three methylation strategies tested. A – Standard stained textiles; B – raw textiles. The values represented are average \pm standard deviation of at least two independent assays, as determined with GC-MS.

of FFA in the raw textiles, and at the different chemical nature of the FAE present in the spin-finishes evaluated here and the acylglycerols present in the standard stains. It should be noted, however, that acylglycerols may also be used as lubricants in spin-finishes (Bajaj, 1997). Therefore, these differences observed in total FA quantification after the methylation protocols may not occur to the same degree in other raw textiles. A previous extraction step was not found to be necessary for an effective methylation, except for lipstick stains, containing large concentrations of waxes (data not shown), with direct acid methylation resulting, in general, in larger amounts of FA analysed than when the acid methylation was carried out after the Bligh & Dyer extraction method (Fig. 1). This is probably due to partition of some lipids to the methanol phase during extraction, as was observed in the recovery rates of palmitic acid, monopalmitin, and dipalmitin after extraction and silylation, as we present below. Direct acid-catalysed methylation, without previous lipid extraction, was thus used for the analysis of all subsequent samples. The GC-FID analysis of palmitic acid derivatised by acid methylation presented a linear peak area/mass concentration response down to a concentration of standard of 0.88 mg L^{-1} ($3.4 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$). The limit of detection obtained in these analyses may be further reduced by decreasing the split ratio of the injector, in relation to the split ratio of 30:1 used in this study.

Silylation reagents MSTFA, BSTFA, and BSTFA+TMCS (99:1) were tested with mixtures of palmitic acid, monopalmitin, and dipalmitin, selected as examples of FFA, MAG, and DAG, present in partially hydrolysed fatty stains. All tested silylation reagents have been previously applied to the derivatisation of FFA and partially hydrolysed acylglycerols (de Carvalho et al., 2016; Firestone, 1994; Lau et al., 2005; Michael-Jubeli et al., 2011; Plank and Lorbeer, 1995). The total concentrations of FFA silylated by MSTFA, BSTFA and BSTFA+TMCS (99:1) in PA1 and C1 were compared to determine the effectiveness of these reagents in the silylation of FFA/FAE present in raw textiles composed of synthetic (PA1) and natural fibres (C1). Synthetic textiles contained spin-finishes whilst natural fibres contained sizing agents. In the present study, MSTFA was less effective at silylating FFA when present in raw textile extracts, under the tested reaction conditions, than BSTFA and BSTFA+TMCS (99:1) (Fig. 2-A). BSTFA+TMCS (99:1) was therefore chosen for the analysis of all raw textile extracts. Additionally, an increase in the concentration of BSTFA+TMCS (99:1) in the reaction media above 10% (v/v) did not lead to an increase in the concentration of the FFA measured in PA1 (Fig. 2-B). After drying, extracts from raw textiles could not be completely dissolved in *n*-hexane. An addition of DMSO at 4% (v/v) was sufficient to solubilise the extract completely. This issue did not occur with standard stains, with DMSO being omitted from these reactions. MSTFA was found to be much more effective for the derivatisation of standards of MAG and DAG than the other silylation reagents under the reaction conditions applied in this study, with a similar performance towards palmitic acid as BSTFA and BSTFA+TMCS (99:1) (Fig. 2-C). As standard stains contain large concentrations of TAG, that are hydrolysed by lipases into DAG, MAG or FFA, this reagent was selected for the silylation of these samples. Increasing the concentration of MSTFA above 10% (v/v) did not lead to an increase in the derivatisation of the FFA/MAG/DAG standards (Fig. 2-D). The concentration of silylation reagent should be kept as low as possible, as it represents the largest cost in these analyses. The GC-FID analysis of TMS derivatives of FFA/MAG/DAG standards presented a linear peak area/mass concentration response down to concentrations of 2.2 mg L^{-1} ($3.9 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$) for dipalmitin, 0.5 mg L^{-1} ($1.52 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$) for monopalmitin, and 0.58 mg L^{-1} ($2.25 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$) for palmitic acid. The Bligh and Dyer extraction of standards and subsequent silylation presented average recovery rates as follows: for palmitic acid of 90.8%, ranging between 87.2% recovery at $375 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$ and 96.7% at $15 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$; of 94.6% for monopalmitin, ranging from 85.9% at $375 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$ and 101% at $5.1 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$; and of 95.6% for dipalmitin, ranging from 86.7% at $375 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$ and 102% at $3.9 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$.

As previously mentioned, the composition of the spin finishes present in a given fibre is frequently unknown to a textile manufacturer. The

Fig. 2. Evaluation of the performance of MSTFA, BSTFA and BSTFA+TMCS (99:1) in the silylation of model substrates. A – silylated FFA relative to FFA silylated with MSTFA, for extracts of raw textiles PA1 and C1; B – Concentration of FFA from PA1, silylated with increasing concentrations of BSTFA + TMCS (99:1), relative to reactions performed with 10% (v/v) of BSTFA + TMCS (99:1); C - Concentration of TMS derivatives of palmitic acid, monopalmitin and dipalmitin (at 0.375 mM), relative to the concentration obtained with MSTFA; D - Concentration of TMS derivatives of palmitic acid, monopalmitin and dipalmitin (at 0.375 mM), silylated with increasing concentrations of MSTFA, relative to reactions performed with 10% (v/v) of MSTFA. The values represented are average \pm standard deviation of at least two independent assays.

application of a silylation protocol to raw textiles would therefore allow for the identification of possible MAG, DAG, and other FAE containing free hydroxyl or carboxyl groups potentially present in the spin finishes. However, no such FAE were found in the raw samples of textiles PA1 and PE1. Significant concentrations of FFA were, nevertheless, present in textiles made of polyamide with elastane (PA1; Fig. 3), polyester (PE1; Fig. 4), and cotton (C1; Fig. 5). Several other peaks could also be observed during the analysis of these samples (supplementary Fig. S1), which were also observed in extracts when no derivatisation protocol was applied. Two FAE, being octyl esters of palmitic or stearic acids, were found in PE1 and PA1, with and without silylation. These FA octyl esters have been patented for application as lubricants in spin finishes (Makino and Taniguchi, 1992; Rellensmann et al., 1977; Robert and Harold, 1965). FA octyl esters did not appear after the acid-catalysed methylation reactions, indicating a complete conversion to FAME, but were still present in samples derivatised with the Instant-FAME™ protocol. Additionally, several peaks with similar MS spectra could be observed in un-derivatised and silylated samples (supplementary Fig. S1), which were identified as oligomers of $\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{O}$ monomers. $\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{O}$ are also the monomers of polydimethylsiloxanes (PDMS), which are silicones widely used as lubricants in the textile industry (Chandra, 1995). Each successive peak in the chromatogram (supplementary Fig. S1) may therefore be matched to PDMS with increasing molecular weights along retention time. It should be noted that the analysis protocol described here was not designed to analyse these compounds, with similar GC protocols only allowing for the analysis of low molecular weight PDMS (Flassbeck et al., 2000; Kala et al., 1997). The protocol should not therefore be applied for the evaluation of the removal of silicones from textiles. Analysis of silylated extracts of raw C1 also presented FFA and PDMS peaks (Fig. 5 and supplementary

Fig. S1—C). Several peaks could not be identified based on the obtained MS spectra in these analyses by lack of appropriate standards or reference compounds in the database.

The two derivatisation methods, methylation and silylation, were thus validated for the analysis of FAE, FFA, and mono/diacylglycerols in textiles. The applicability of these methodologies in the evaluation of the performance of lipases in textile treatments was subsequently assessed. For this, silylation and methylation were applied in the analysis of textiles containing spin-finishes or with standard lipid stains, after treatment with lipases, as is presented in the following sections.

3.2. Enzyme performance for spin-finish removal from fabrics after manufacturing

The lipase-assisted spin-finish removal process was divided into two steps: enzyme treatment and washing. First, raw textiles were treated with lipases by padding with a Foulard machine, leading to the retention of a volume of enzyme and buffer solution in the textile below saturation. The textile was then incubated for a given period of time, after which it was washed with the aim of removing the hydrolysis products and other components of the spin-finish.

For the raw textiles treated with lipases, no significant reduction in concentration of fatty acids after washing could be attributed to the enzyme treatment (Figs. 3 to 5). However, a substantial increase in concentration of FFA occurred in PA1 (Fig. 3-C), indicating that the lipases tested were active towards the FAE present in this textile. A comparison of the fatty acid profiles of the raw and treated PA1 textiles showed that the small decrease in the total FA concentration observed after washing was disproportionately due to the removal of FAE containing hexadecanoic and octadecanoic acids (Fig. 3-B). An exception to

Fig. 3. Analysis of total FA and of FFA on textile PA1, including samples of raw textile (Raw), textile after current industrial pre-treatment process (Pre-treated), and raw textile samples treated in the assay with enzymes, or with buffer alone (No Enzyme). A – total concentration of FA; B – FA profile, obtained after methylation; C – concentration of FFA; D – FFA profile, obtained after silylation; E – Concentration of octyl esters in treated samples relative to concentration in the raw textile. The values represented are average \pm standard deviation of at least two independent assays.

this were the samples treated with Lip9, which presented a lower proportion of octadecenoic acid than those treated with the remaining enzymes. However, the FFA profiles (Fig. 3-D) of the textiles subjected to enzymatic treatment were similar to those of the total FA (Fig. 3-B), indicating that the enzymes were able to hydrolyse the FAE without significant selectivity issues towards esters containing specific FA, although the difference in selectivity between Lip9 and the remaining enzymes is apparent. Additionally, the FA octyl esters previously identified in PA1 presented a substantial decrease in concentration after enzyme treatment when compared to the original untreated textile (Fig. 3-E). This further confirms the activity of the tested lipases. The lack of an overall decrease in concentration of total FA indicates that FFA were not substantially more soluble in the aqueous media than the original FAE under the washing conditions used. Different factors affecting the solubility of FFA, such as pH of the washing solution or the addition of surfactants (Glücklich et al., 2020), must be explored to take advantage of the lipase treatment in the removal of spin finishes.

In PE1, the tested lipases did not show activity towards the FAE present, as no improvement in the removal of total FA or increase in FFA occurred in the samples treated with the enzymes when compared to the “no enzyme” controls (Fig. 4). On the other hand, the increase in FA concentrations observed in “no enzyme” C1 samples after washing in comparison to “Raw” samples (Fig. 5-A), can be attributed to the removal of water-soluble components of the sizing agent, which led to an increase in the concentration of insoluble compounds in relation to total sample mass. Therefore, some removal of FAE may have occurred due to the lipase treatment of C1 textiles, given the decrease in concentration of FA observed between “no enzyme” controls and textiles treated with enzymes (Fig. 5-A), although this could not be confirmed by the silylation analysis, as no significant increase in FFA after enzyme treatment could be observed (Fig. 5-B).

Although the authors of this study acknowledge that both methylation and silylation methods followed by GC analysis, either by GC-FID or GC-MS, may not be readily available in most laboratories, the

Fig. 4. Analysis of total FA and of FFA on textile PE1, including samples of raw textile (Raw), textile after current industrial pre-treatment process (Pre-treated), and raw textile samples treated in the assay with enzymes, or with buffer alone (No Enzyme). A – total concentration of FA, determined after methylation; B – concentration of FFA, obtained after silylation. The values represented are average \pm standard deviation of at least two independent assays.

Fig. 5. Analysis of total FA and of FFA on textile C1, including samples of raw textile (Raw), textile after current industrial pre-treatment process (Pre-treated), and raw textile samples treated in the assay with enzymes, or with buffer alone (No Enzyme). A – total concentration of FA; B – concentration of FFA. The values represented are average \pm standard deviation of at least two independent assays.

proposed methodology allows for the identification and quantification of enzyme products during removal of spin-finishes and desizing of textiles. Classical titration and methods based on e.g. colourimetry, voltametry, and conductivity often require large amounts of solvents and provide no information on the identification of the FFA (Uçar et al., 2024). Spectroscopic methods such as Raman, Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR), and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectroscopy allow the determination of structural groups and molecular structure of non-derivatised compounds, but chromatographic methods such as GC-FID and GC-MS provide easy quantification and identification of substrates and products (Hawkes and Lewis, 2025; Uçar et al., 2024). GC-MS has also been used e.g. to successfully determine the fatty acid content of wool and to determine the efficacy of “delipidation” processes (Hawkes and Lewis, 2025).

3.3. Enzyme performance for fat stains removal from standard stained textiles

Under the MS scan parameters used in this study, the GC-MS analyses presented relatively low sensitivity towards silylated compounds, when compared to the response observed e.g. for methylated compounds. In fact, no TMS derivatives of DAG could be identified in the enzyme treated Beef-fat-stained fabric samples in the GC-MS chromatograms. However, a substantial increase in the number and area of peaks was observed with the GC-FID analysis of these samples compared to samples that were not subject to lipase hydrolysis, including peaks with RT equal to or larger than those of TMS derivatives of dipalmitin

(supplementary Fig. S2). For this analysis, all peaks with a RT equal or larger to the TMS derivatives of dipalmitin, absent in untreated samples, were identified as presumptive DAG.

The treatment of standard Beef-fat-stained fabric with lipase Y250S led to a large decrease in the total concentration of FA in the textile, of $62.6\% \pm 0.8\%$, when compared to textiles treated without lipase, which presented a reduction of $6.8\% \pm 1.2\%$ (Fig. 6-A). Simultaneously, a large increase in the concentration of FFA, MAG and DAG occurred in these samples (Fig. 6-B, C and D). In addition to the total FA results, this offers further confirmation of the activity of Y250S towards the TAG in the Beef-fat stain. The concentrations of FFA, MAG and DAG in the analyses do not account for the totality of theoretical products from the hydrolysis reactions that occurred in these samples. As shown by the decrease in total FA, a large proportion of these lipids was removed from the textiles treated with Y250S during the 5 h incubation at 40 °C. This occurred despite the absence of surfactants in the reaction. Additionally, the stained textiles, originally pink in colour, due to the addition of Sudan red dye, became nearly white after lipase treatment (Fig. 6-E), with the final reaction media presenting pink oily residues.

For the standard Mayonnaise-stained fabric, a smaller decrease in total FA due to lipase hydrolysis was observed, with a $32.7\% \pm 7.4\%$ reduction in FA concentration in enzyme treated samples, compared with a $22.9\% \pm 2.7\%$ reduction in “no enzyme” controls (Fig. 7-A). An increase in concentration of FFA, but not in MAG, could also be observed in samples treated with lipase. No DAG could be observed in these samples. The accumulation of FFA in these samples, with low concentrations of both MAG and DAG, indicates that Y250S is capable of

Fig. 6. Analysis of total FA and of FFA on Beef-fat-stained fabric after treatment with the enzyme Y250S. A – total concentration of FA; B – concentration of FFA; C – concentration of MAG; D – concentration of DAG. The values represented are average \pm standard deviation of at least two independent assays. E – Visual appearance of Beef-fat-stained fabric, before treatment, and after treatment with Y250S.

catalysing the complete hydrolysis of TAG into FFA and glycerol.

The International Association for Soaps, Detergents and Maintenance Products (A.I.S.E.) published laundry detergent testing guidelines where the efficiency of stain removal is determined by reflectance via spectrophotometer (A.I.S.E., 2023). The same method is recommended in the “Revised EU Ecolabel protocol for testing laundry detergents” (Directorate-General for Environment, 2023). Although this is a cheap method that has been used to assess the efficacy of detergents containing enzymes, and which can be carried out by non-specialised personnel, it does not provide in-depth information on the reaction performed by the enzyme(s). The protocol proposed in the present study, allows for both the determination of the products of the enzyme biotransformation and the efficacy of the washing procedure. By comparing the total fatty acid content and the free fatty acids in the samples, it is possible to infer on the enzyme activity and mass transfer issues related to the solubility of products and/or adhesion of products to fibres.

4. Conclusion

Two derivatisation methods, methylation and silylation, were applied in this study for the characterisation of FAE present in textiles, with the aim of evaluating the performance of lipases for their removal from the fibres. The two silylation strategies evaluated in the study, on the other hand, offer specific information on the performance of the target lipases with FAE substrates.

The two applications of lipases to textile treatments, (i) removal of

spin-finish/size and (ii) removal of fatty stains, the former being of primary relevance to the textile industry and the latter to the detergent industry, illustrate the usefulness of the two derivatisation techniques proposed in this study. With methylation, the ineffectiveness of the washing procedure applied to raw textiles in these assays was clearly demonstrated. However, its application alone would not have shown that the lipases were active towards the FAE in PA1, as was demonstrated with silylation. Similarly, methylation allowed for the quantification of the removal of acylglycerols/FAE from the Beef-fat stain with the lipase treatment. However, for the Mayonnaise stain, little improvement in the removal of FAE could be observed after the lipase treatment. Using silylation, it became evident that the lipase had hydrolysed TAG in these samples. By simultaneously analysing FFA, MAG and DAG, it could also be determined that TAG were mostly being fully hydrolysed into glycerol and FFA. Likewise, the comparison between FA and FFA profiles allowed for the evaluation of the promiscuity of the three lipases towards the FAE present in PA1. The information about enzyme specificity afforded by these techniques may be of further use, for instance, in the development of lipase cocktails for the treatment of textiles containing complex FAE mixtures for which the application of a single enzyme may not be sufficient to reach complete hydrolysis. Testing lipases directly with the textiles in combination with subsequent analysis proved to be very useful to evaluate enzyme activity. It is known that the removal of fat/oil and its hydrolysis products from a stained textile during laundry washing does not solely depend on the activity of a lipase (Sonesson et al., 2007). Hence, this approach can be useful to

Fig. 7. Analysis of total FA and of FFA on Mayonnaise-stained fabric after treatment with the enzyme Y250S. A – total concentration of FA; B – concentration of FFA; C – concentration of MAG. The values represented are average \pm standard deviation of at least two independent assays.

identify lipases to formulate, for example, more efficient detergents.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Luís C. de Sousa: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Nazanin Ansari:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation. **Roland Lottenbach:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation. **Rainer Rösch:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Jan Modregger:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Simona Capone:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation. **Karl-Erich Jaeger:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Rebecka Molitor:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation. **Stephan Thies:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation. **Paula Vidal:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation. **Manuel Ferrer:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Carla C.C.R. de Carvalho:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

N. Ansari, R. Lottenbach, and R. Rösch worked at Schoeller Textil AG, a company producing fabrics. J. Modregger and S. Capone work for Biosynth GmbH, a manufacturer of enzymes among other biologics and chemicals.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biteb.2026.102699>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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